

Emerging Trends and Technologies for Green Building Construction In India

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Abstract Green building is a technique that tries to lessen harmful effects on the environment and public health, making it more sustainable than traditional building techniques. Though, green practices and technology are being promoted at large, the concept of green construction in India has not yet developed to the point where it may have a more significant impact on society. This article looks at the future of green buildings and associated emerging technologies required for its adoption in the Indian sub-continent through literature review and analysis. According to the study, there is a significant opportunity for the widespread construction of green buildings in India, but obstacles include skillful green building professionals, lack of effective laws and incentives, and weaknesses in processing and communication. Futuristic technologies like Building information modeling, smart facades and Green materials will pave way for better sustainable construction growth in India.

Keywords Building Information modeling, adaptive facades, green buildings, Sustainable construction.

Introduction

Indian cities are facing environmental and resource issues due to an ever-growing population, rapid urbanization, and economic growth. Nevertheless, the need for development cannot be denied, there arises a search for sustainable development. Green Building Construction is a significant solution to sustainable growth in India. By 2030, India's 68 cities will have a population more than one million and the urban sectors alone will have a population of around 590 million. In cities, High rise buildings are already escalating due to the space constraints and materials are depleting at a faster rate. Green Building Technology is a promising tool to balance between urban growth and the effective utilization of natural resources. Parameters like Climate responsive design, use of local & recycled materials, sustainable water management, harnessing natural resources, waste recycling etc., paves the way for long lasting sustainable buildings. Projections from the industry reports that the green building market in India is expected to reach US\$ 30–40 billion by 2030 and will generate an investment potential of 1.4 trillion USD, according to estimations by the International Finance Corporation (IFC). The same report mentions that the green building market in India will provide an investment potential of \$1.4T by 2030, reaching US\$30-\$40 billion (IFC). Already, numerous entrepreneurs are attempting to reduce the carbon footprint of the construction industry and promote sustainability by offering green solutions as they see this as significant economic opportunity. Under the leadership of the Prime Minister's Science, Technology, and Innovation Advisory Council (PM-STIAC), the AGNI Mission, a key project of the Office of the Principal Scientific Adviser (PSA) to the Government of India, actively supports numerous start-ups that are offering novel, sustainable, and affordable solutions for green building. Adoption of "Green" construction principles are a fact that is evident in several major cities, including Bangalore, Delhi, and New Mumbai. The Confederation of Indian Industry (CII) founded the Indian Green Construction Council (IGBC) in 2001 with the goal of creating a sustainable environment for all, and since then, more than 7,128 green building projects have been registered with this organization. Many of these initiatives have received certification and are fully operating. According to these statistics, there is a huge economic opportunity due to the increased demand for professionals with in-depth understanding of the sector, such as architects, energy specialists, and technicians. As a result, there is a tremendous opportunity for entrepreneurs to develop technology in this developing industrial sector and establish green building as a new norm and standard. India has started its green building movement gradually with its own green rating systems (Hema et al. 2021) thanks to the establishment of Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment (GRIHA) by The Energy Resources Institute (TERI) and MNRE and Indian Green Building Council (IGBC) by Confederation of Indian Industry (CII). This paper discusses the numerous prospects for green building development focused on enhancing resource efficiency in the Indian sub-continent. Also, this paper brings forward some of the emerging areas in green technology, namely, Building Information Modeling, Green Cements and Smart & Adaptive facades that paves way for sustainable construction in India today.

Building Information Modeling

Green and sustainable construction is gaining momentum over the past few years. The contribution of Building Information Modeling (BIM) to achieve sustainable building construction is recently recognized by the construction sector. The steps towards achieving sustainable design can be perceived when effective decisions are made during the project inception stage itself (Bui et al. 2016). Existing methods of construction do not support the energy and performance studies during the design stages of buildings. Hence, an integrated approach is void in the design procedure that ends up in redesigning a part or whole of the building, thereby wasting time and resources. As we progress towards more sustainable approaches in construction, not only should the design and materials be resource-efficient, the application of processes should also be environmentally responsible. Generally, sustainable construction

strives to enhance living environments for individuals and communities; requires minimal energy and generates minimal waste over the course of its lifecycle and integrates with the natural environment. It is surprising to understand that even buildings that are 'Platinum' rated by the 'Green rating systems' across the globe, consume a lot in terms of energy. It is mainly due to the fact that the majority of current assessment standards find it difficult to incorporate the operation and maintenance phase of a project after it has been completed. Building Information Modeling is a recent tool that may help to streamline sustainability in the three major construction phases namely, Design, Construction and Maintenance Phase supporting the entire life cycle Fig. 1 of a built environment. In the design phase, the project team can have a real-time summary of all the materials and products involved in a project and analyze their performance expectations. This leads to adopt only the materials that are environmentally responsible that offers savings in time and money, which may otherwise be spent on reworking and rescheduling. Moreover, the 3D models provided by BIM streamline real-time collaboration and simulation at every level of the design and construction phase, enabling review and improvising at every stage. BIM can help designers to conduct a life cycle assessment (LCA) of the building and helps to optimize design strategies during the initial stage. BIM includes many kinds of software applications for different functionalities and strengths. For example, 'Autodesk Revit' supports not only architectural and structural design, but also includes building services. Alternatively, 'Design builder' has its application in simulation and modeling for building energy consumption (Cheng at al. 2020) including heating, cooling, lighting, and ventilation, etc. BIM is closely aligned to design for manufacture and assembly (DFMA). By reducing conventional approaches in construction, this technique can actually improve quality of workmanship and worker safety, offers better quality and greater durability, reduces transportation and associated fuel consumption, lowers carbon emissions and helps overall sustainability. A few construction professionals are already considering these aspects when designing their projects' parameters, which include operational recommendations and maintenance schedules designed for a long-term, environmentally friendly future. Adding to these, integrative design, multiple stakeholder collaboration, unified approach, effective presentation and speedy decision-making aspects of BIM are an integral part to sustainable design processes.

Fig. 1. BIM Integrated Sustainable Design

Usage of BIM for Green Infrastructure in India

India is expected to experience rapid urbanization and economic expansion. This increase will necessitate a lot of building work; therefore it will need to be properly planned, scheduled, designed, and managed in terms of information. Strong implementation frameworks, trustworthy technology tools as well as advanced design communication, project collaboration, and documentation are necessary to meet these objectives. The construction industry in India has enormous demands, and BIM can serve as a model that can significantly drive to improve those needs. The precision with which BIM models can assimilate and integrate data improves the clarity and sharpness of communication between the project stakeholders- owners; builders and contractors. It serves as a launching pad for the use of cutting-edge technology in the construction sector, including robotics and artificial intelligence. The quantity and type of structures being built changed noticeably during the start of this millennium. The number of structures with modern HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems, intelligence requirements, and energy needs is growing. An interactive tool that accurately simulates the project's complexity, compiles all the data in one location, and bridges the information across all the model's objects is imperative in this situation. The original interest in BIM was sparked by this. However, the majority of professionals in the field weren't originally drawn to this technology. Initial barriers to BIM adoption included lack of experience with a new technology tool, a lack of knowledge, the expenses associated, reluctance to change long-standing traditions, and other similar issues. BIM has revolutionized the construction industry by its comprehensive and collaborative method for managing data for construction projects. BIM connects teams and transdisciplinary data in the cloud using intelligent and digital methodologies to enable real time information of all construction phases from planning to design, as opposed to the traditional 2D representational approach. This approach

has significantly increased the productivity and efficiency of businesses in the construction sector over the last few years. India has emerged as a nation with potential investors and BIM-capable personnel due to the recent growth of BIM implementation in the country's construction industry, both in the public and private sectors Table 1. India's population is anticipated to overtake China by 2025, and thus, there is an increased need for infrastructure, classroom space, and social housing. According to a study conducted by the Asian Journal of Civil Engineering (Hire et al. 2021), there has been a significant rise in awareness of BIM among Indian construction experts. There isn't yet a BIM mandate in India. Users at the project level have been the main drivers of BIM adoption. The accomplishment of these initiatives' and goals encourages gradual BIM adoption at the organizational level. Adoption has primarily occurred in the private sector. Special driving mechanism was established in the public sector promoting BIM adoption through regulations. Because of the magnitude of projects and the simplicity of cost control, public sector has quickly responded to BIM acquisition in India. Nearly all development projects (metro) are now required to use 5D BIM (Dhopte et al. 2022) as a result of the adoption of 5D BIM for Nagpur- MAHA Metro project. In a similar vein, infrastructure projects are increasingly stepping towards mandating digital integration platforms in projects throughout the development's lifecycle in addition to BIM mandates for construction management. This includes integrating 5D cost management tools with ERP tools and drawings, 3D models and simulation software for construction. Working together, BIM should be put in use in all of its forms (from 3D to 8D) in infrastructural projects. For the majority of projects, it will only cost 1% of the total project-cost to realize long term benefits like timely material acquisition, prompt project completion, regular supplier payment schedules, and more. Additionally, the BIM Academy noted that by 2040, India will need to make a significant expenditure of roughly 4.5 trillion dollars to improve infrastructure in order to achieve its projected economic development. The BIM technique has already been implemented by significant Indian AEC companies in their projects. The challenges that prevent India from fully implementing BIM nationwide are not unique to India. The most pertinent ones, according to businesses, are the high expenses associated with this digital transition, the dearth of BIM-qualified personnel. Being aware of the advantages of BIM, they might be able to quickly recoup their investment in updating building procedures thanks to it. Due to the country's construction industry's rapid expansion, the Indian government would soon need to invest in and take action to implement BIM in the AEC sector. Fair enough, the Indian government has already taken significant actions to integrate and utilize BIM. The International Airport – Bangalore, PRTS (Personal Rapid Transit System) of Amritsar, Delhi Metro Rail, Nagpur Metro Rail and the renovation of Gwalior Railway Station are just a few of the large infrastructure projects that has deployed the framework of BIM methodology. Despite being aware of the benefits of BIM, Indian construction businesses have not completely utilized it (Ahuja et al. 2020). Open BIM standards are used in nations like Norway and Austria due of their benefits. Countries leading in BIM adoption include the United States of America (USA), the United Kingdom (UK), Singapore, Finland, Sweden, Russia, Denmark, Australia, Korea, and Dubai, whose governments have made BIM mandatory for construction processes (Shimonti et al. 2018). Some nations are preparing mandates for the near future. On the other hand, BIM acceptance is progressively rising in some nations like India. Additionally, there are significant, long-standing societies whose goals are to plan and present BIM events to educate professionals about the newest developments in this technology and promote the digital transformation of businesses and individuals working in the AEC sector. These include the Indian Building Information Modeling Association, which was established in April 2019, and the BIM Summit, which Parveen Sharme, CEO of the BIM Engineers, spoke about the adoption of BIM in India at in August 2018. The high cost of BIM software and the shortage of BIM professionals were the two biggest factors affecting the world BIM market in 2015, according to a global opportunity analysis and industry prediction for the period 2015–2022. Additionally, interoperability will increase productivity in 2022, while government mandates for BIM and rising energy and efficiency concerns will also have a significant impact. In light of this, it is crucial for the Indian AECO industry to keep this in mind and concentrate on the aforementioned three factors: interoperability, energy and resource efficiency, and government BIM regulations.

Green Cement

In the past few decades, researchers have been searching for alternatives to cement that are safer, cheaper, and more viable. A good sustainable alternative is the 'Green Cement'. Green cement can be defined as "A cementitious material that possesses the functional capabilities of ordinary Portland cement and is sustainable in terms of lower consumption of natural resources." By incorporating sustainable measures, green cement can be produced in a number of ways. A key objective of green cement is to reduce carbon emission, use less energy in manufacturing, use industrial waste as raw materials, maintain high strength for a long time, have greater ductility, reduce porosity, and enhance mechanical strength. In order to achieve this, the cement manufacturing process needs to be modified in a way that will reduce emissions significantly (Mohamad et al. 2022). Green cement is a kind of cement produced out of a carbon-negative approach of manufacturing (Naqi et al. 2019) with a view of minimizing the carbon footprint of cement production and aims to resolve serious environmental issues. It is, however, necessary to raise awareness about green cement and its potential in the present scenario. Presently, multiple patented technologies and mechanisms are available for green cement manufacture by different manufacturing agencies. Green cement manufacture reduces cement intake, and adopts discarded industrial wastes like blast furnace slag and fly ash (Brito and Kurda 2021) as the major raw materials. Compared to conventional cements, the manufacturing process of green cement reduces the carbon dioxide emissions even up to 40%. In addition to this, ingredients like calcined clay and powdered limestone offers improved mechanical strength and reduced porosity to green cements. Additionally, these goals can be achieved by using less energy -

Table 1. Application of BIM in Major Projects in India

Name of the Project	BIM Application
Personal Rapid Transit in Amritsar	Scheduling, Planning, Designing, Construction
Bangalore Airport	Autodesk BIM 360 as the design and planning of platform for the construction of the Terminal 2
Neggur/Nagpur Metro Rail Corporation	the integration of 5D BIM technology
Delhi Metro Rail	Used BIM technology for construction of the underground track

intensive and low-cost alternative fuels, such as ground limestone (reduces carbon emissions and costs) and ground granulated blast furnace slag (works at low temperature and needs less energy). Other interventions can be the usage of resource efficient cement mixes. For example, Calcium Sulfo-aluminate cement, which requires comparatively less energy and releases less carbon; Calcium Aluminate cement, which produces comparatively less carbon; Magnesium-oxide cement, which absorbs more carbon (requires less energy to produce). In addition, Alkali-activated cement is also a good alternative due to its similar performance and cost to ordinary Portland cement, but it produces a much lower amount of carbon dioxide, is durable, and utilizes industrial waste as raw material, thus helping with recycling (Marinelli et al. 2022). In India, a large number of companies are currently producing green cement for consumer use. Despite their differences, they share the goal of offering cement alternatives that are cleaner and more environmentally friendly. A cement manufacturing unit has also claimed to achieve Zero-carbon footprint which produces cement using fly ash and liquid additives. Construction is essential for humankind and so is cement. The main idea now, is to reduce the consumption or to reverse the impacts that have been caused by the conventional methods of construction. Every industry, being in a position to move towards sustainable, it is high time cement manufacturers should look for an alternative to go green.

Smart and Adaptive Facades

Smart and adaptive facades have gained momentum due to the search for low-energy consumption and energy harvesting green buildings recently. An adaptive building is designed to perform better in terms of energy efficiency and/or comfort under a variety of user demands (Mohammed et al. 2019), indoor circumstances, and external factors like weather and season. A number of adaptive facade technologies and products are available in the market Fig.2 which includes dynamic solar shading, electro-chromic glazing, and phase change materials (Attia et al. 2020). Experts and researchers recommend four major technologies that have high projected market opportunities by 2050. These are: Dynamic-shading, Chromogenic, Solar active and Active ventilative facades. Dynamic facades aim to control daylight, improve thermal insulation, suitable for summer comfort and offers cooling savings. Provision of shutters, roller blinds, venetian blinds is few examples. Chromogenic facades are directly integrated in the glazing which includes electro-chromic glazing, liquid crystal glazing, and thermo-chromic glazing. The benefit is that their physical characteristics can be changed in accordance, modifying the glazing's look (Boke et al.2020) and varying its degree of transparency. Solar active facades are helpful for controlling sunlight (Matin et al. 2022) and achieving comfort in the summer and winter. Some of the commonly used technologies here are: Phase change materials, double skin facades, Building integrated PV, green facades and roofs (Heidari et al. 2022). Active ventilative facades are based on ventilation, and use two technologies: actively ventilated CCFs which regulates the airflow inside the cavity, and automated operable windows which control the entry of air inside the building. Further, the upcoming technologies in smart and adaptive structures incorporate digitalization and artificial intelligence approaches, and few inspiring buildings are recently constructed in India Table.2. In order to give value, smart and adaptive techniques need a sophisticated collection of skills for storing, integrating, analyzing, reacting, anticipating, and subsequently learning from user input. The structural trend of the digitalization of living, working, and educational environments forces all stakeholders in façade solutions to raise the value of their facade solutions. Building operating system (BOS) is one such trending application for smart

Fig.2. (Tabadkani et

Adaptive Facades al. 2021)

adaptive facades. BOS is the primary software platform for smart facades because it makes it easy to implement and manage digital and IoT applications inside of buildings. In order to develop communication between a variety of building service systems, sensors, control interfaces and personal devices, it intends to transform an adaptive facade into a digital service platform. This provides an occupant-centered facility with an integrated self-learned intelligence. Future study in these areas should focus on the responsiveness and automated controllability of adaptive facades. Yet, significant research is required in near future to evaluate the potential of adaptive facades towards addressing environmentally, socially, and economically aspects. Integrating different aspects of façade performance, Integration between the building and its occupants and integrating the façade and the technology (Balali et al.2020) are the major factors influencing the Design of dynamic facades. Kinetic architecture may offer a way to design places that are more adaptive, safe, structured, and friendly to the environment while also improving the quality of the built environment. Simple kinetic systems created with materials and methods native to the region will be most suited. If the characteristics and lifespan of the materials are improved, material deformation will be effective. Comparatively, Kinetic elements with whole dynamism can be achieved through elements that are affordable as well as sufficient and sustainable. India is a tropical monsoon climate and Climate varies all over India. In places like Delhi, the summer and winter are extreme. Hence dynamic/kinetic elements that respond extreme temperatures will be quite effective. In case of places with uniform solar radiation, dynamic elements for heat alone may be sufficient.

Table 2. Buildings with Adaptive façade systems in India

Name of the Project	Adaptive facade component	Type of Facility	Image of the Facility
Krusha Bhawan, Odisha	The façade is made out of a brick-louvered screen that expresses local weaving patterns and serves as a solar shaver. The colours used in the screen's design reflect the region's ethnic diversity.	Government facility	
72 Screens, Jaipur	Facade comprises of Lightweight screens that are made of Glass Fiber Reinforced Concrete, (GFRC) for thermal comfort	Office Building	

Hexalace,
Mohali

A layer of semi-permeable concrete-three inches thick with hexagonal cut-out sections serves as a shading element.

Open-plan
Commercial
Building

Temenos,
New Delhi

The façade is inspired by origami-folds, a double-skin of perforated aluminum panels rendered in rich champagne color. The perforations have been precisely tuned to prevent solar glare and dampen external noise to create a tranquil indoor user-experience.

Commercial
Complex

Hive House,
Surat

The geometry of the solar-sensor based façade is influenced by hexagonal structural patterns found in nature

Residential
Building

KMC
Corporate
Office,
Hyderabad

The double skin layer acts as a visually dynamic façade and also screens the humidifying air entering the building for evaporative cooling. The outer layer has aluminium trellis with hydroponic trays integrated for growing a variety of plants.

Corporate
Building

Pearl Academy of Fashion, Jaipur

Modern adaptation of traditional Indo-Islamic architectural elements and passive-cooling design strategies

Residential Building

Cybertecture Egg, Mumbai

An innovative column-less steel diagrid shell structure incorporated with passive solar design to decrease heat gain and lower energy loads cool the building envelope.

Office Building

Moving Landscapes, Ahmedabad

Built with Smart automation, allowing occupants to vary the amount of light, ventilation, and privacy in their home. Sliding and spinning walls animate the façade of this house. 1'6" mm thick Bidaser stone panels pivot in alternate directions or back and forth in some areas to protect the inner layer of glass and concrete.

Residential Building

The Street, Mathura

Each room has a unique wedge-shaped bay window oriented towards the north minimizing the heat gain in response to the climate, creating a separate identity for each.

800-foot Student Housing Complex

To be dynamic, a building should only have a small number of moving components and this is known as kinetic architecture. The evolution of smart materials makes its implementation easier. In addition to being aesthetically pleasing, kinetic architecture also benefits the environment by reducing solar heat gain (Ghaffarian Hoseini et al. 2013) and enhancing building efficiency. Dynamic automated systems may also increase costs. Systems that are manually operated are less expensive; however pre-programmed automated systems that use sensors and detectors might increase costs. However, these applications are useful for conceptual reasons, audience attraction, and representing cultural and social factors.

Upcoming Techniques and Materials

The green building technology provides us with tremendous opportunities to reverse the damages we have done to our planet and the environment. For instance, futuristic technologies like Air cleaning materials will make our indoor and outdoor environments healthier; Micro-grids, net-zero buildings, electricity-generating windows and carbon sequestering materials will help reduce fuel/energy consumption and their associated greenhouse-gas-emissions. Smart glass will help to enhance our indoor environments more comfortable and becomes less energy intensive to heat and cool, saving energy and money. The building sector accounts for roughly 39% of the world's energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions, making them one of the greatest causes of climate change. One-tenth of all greenhouse gas emissions are due to embodied carbon. Straw, wood, linoleum, and cedar are examples of materials that store carbon and can actually take in atmospheric carbon dioxide and store it within the walls of the building. The building industry could someday transition from being a significant carbon emitter to a carbon sink through careful material selection. The embodied carbon footprint rises when carbon-intensive materials are used in construction. It is possible to attain a zero-net carbon structure if buildings are constructed to be carbon sinks. Additionally, such buildings when equipped with renewable sources of energy can possibly reverse climate change as well. Recent researches include utilization of biological building materials as an opportunity to reduce the construction industry's environmental impact. The overall cement production around the world is more than 4 billion tonnes per year, which accounts for 8% of the world's CO₂ emissions. If bio-based materials can replace some percentage of existing building materials, this new technique could actually sequester CO₂ from the atmosphere. Bio-concrete is a one such technology (Peplow et al. 2020) wherein concrete is seeded with bacterial spores and calcium lactate. The bacterial spores remain inactive and get activated only when it comes in contact with water, initiating lactate digestion and produce CO₂. In concrete's highly alkaline environment, solid calcium carbonate is formed when CO₂ reacts with calcium ions. This can seal cracks up to 1 mm wide within a few weeks and prevent further water ingress. Thus bio-concrete has become a promising technology for self-healing of concrete (Iqbal et al. 2021). If the demand for bio-concrete increases, it may reduce the consumption of cement in buildings and also due to its self-healing property, it would definitely improve the overall sustainability in building construction.

Conclusion

Developing sustainable materials and green technologies can also add commercial values for environment-friendly solutions and enabling a circular economy in the built-up sector to ultimately reduce the carbon footprint. Some of the main areas of focus in the near future are as follows: up cycling of plastic wastes to fuels and fine chemicals; bio-plastics for a circular economy; new functional materials from renewable biomass (Ahamed et al. 2022) and industrial by-products and green technologies for renewable energy and thermal management. Sustainable building construction is a holistic approach for resource management. The modern architecture imbibes the concept of sustainability to bring out green buildings. Earlier, 1 tonne of cement equalled nearly 1 tonne of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in terms of CO₂. At present, thanks to the adoption of sustainable measures in the cement manufacturing processes, the emissions are reduced to 0.7 to 0.75 tonnes of CO₂ per tonne of cement. The green buildings have shown 20 – 40% savings in electricity consumption bills and 40-65% reduction in water consumption. In India, there will be more than 10,000 registered green buildings by 2020, and many of them will be using green building technologies. With a market size rise of 35 to 50 billion dollars by 2022 and area coverage of more than 10 billion square feet, India has the potential to become a global leader in the field of green building technology.

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